

ISic3629

I.Sicily inscription 3629

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

dedication

Material

tuff

Object

stele

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Selinus

Place of origin (modern)

Selinunte

Provenance

in situ in the 'Campo di stele di Zeus Meilichios', near the
three-betyl altar

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Selinunte, Parco Archeologico di Selinunte

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: EDR120815

1. [---] Μι
2. [λ]ίχιος ἔ [μὶ]
- 3.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 285087

EDR 120815

EDCS 64400282

Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 59.1120

Grotta, C. 2010. Zeus Meilichios a Selinunte. Rome. At 114 no.6

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